

M Modern approaches to the organization of arterial hypertension prevention

Enfoques modernos para la organización de la prevención de la hipertensión arterial

Farid Kurbanalievich Kurbanaliev Saratov State Medical University named after V.I.Razumovsky Saratov, Bolshaya Kazachya str., 112, 410012. <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0418-5835>, ridkv@mail.ru

Zumrut Ilmanovna Stambulova Saratov State Medical University named after V. I. Razumovsky, 112 Bolshaya Kazachya, 410012, Saratov, Russia. zumrut.stambulova@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2714-7005>

Zamira Kerimovna Azizova Saratov State Medical University named after V. I. Razumovsky, 112 Bolshaya Kazachya, 410012, Saratov, Russia. azizovazami19@yandex.ru, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9408-7828>

Liubov Lisienkova Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University) 26, Yaroslavskoe shosse, Moscow, 129337, Russia, lisienkova@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0897-3387>

Adam Dukuvahaevich Baialiev Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education «Astrakhan State Medical University» Medical Faculty 414000, Astrakhan, Bakinskaya str. 121, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6940-639X> . www.adambaialiev95@gmail.com

Ekaterina Viktorovna Zorkina Pirogov Russian National Research Medical University, 1 Ostrovityanova st., Moscow 117513, Russia. ekaterina.zorkina2000@gmail.com. <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7291-9240>

Alexander Markov Tyumen State Medical University, Tyumen, Russian Federation Tyumen Industrial University, Tyumen, Russian Federation. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7471-4792>, alexdoctor@inbox.ru

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Abstract

The article studies modern approaches to the prevention of diseases of the musculoskeletal apparatus (MSA). Diseases of the musculoskeletal system, such as osteochondrosis, arthritis, osteoporosis and others, significantly reduce the quality of life of patients and can lead to disability. Therefore, prevention of these diseases becomes an important task of the health care system. The article analyzes the main risk factors contributing to the development of MSA, and pathology, among which insufficient physical activity, improper nutrition, non-compliance with ergonomic rules, unfavorable working conditions and hereditary predispositions stand out. Examples are given of effective exercise programs that promote musculoskeletal health, strengthen muscles and joints, and improve flexibility and mobility. Methods of workplace adaptation to reduce stress on the spine and joints are discussed, as well as the importance of maintaining correct posture and taking regular breaks during the working day. Modern methods of early diagnosis of musculoskeletal disorders, such as digital radiography, MRI, CT scanning, and digital technology to monitor the patient's condition and predict the risk of disease development are utilised. The results emphasise the need for a comprehensive approach to the prevention of MSA diseases, including not only the participation of doctors of various specialties, such as orthopedists, neurologists and physiotherapists but also interdisciplinary interaction with representatives of other spheres, including employers and ergonomics specialists.

Keywords: prevention, MSA diseases (MSDs), musculoskeletal system, MSA risk factors, physical activity, ergonomics.

Resumen

El artículo examina los enfoques modernos para la prevención y el tratamiento de la hipertensión arterial (presión arterial alta), una condición de creciente relevancia debido al aumento de los estilos de vida sedentarios, los cambios en la dieta y el envejecimiento de la población mundial. La hipertensión arterial es un importante factor de riesgo de enfermedades cardiovasculares como accidentes cerebrovasculares, ataques cardíacos e insuficiencia renal, lo que reduce significativamente la calidad de vida y aumenta el riesgo de mortalidad. Por tanto, controlar y prevenir la hipertensión arterial es una prioridad para los sistemas sanitarios de todo el mundo. Los autores del artículo analizan los principales factores de riesgo que contribuyen al desarrollo de la hipertensión, entre los que se incluyen el consumo excesivo de sal, la obesidad, la inactividad física, el tabaquismo, el estrés y las predisposiciones genéticas. Se presta especial atención a las medidas preventivas destinadas a reducir estos factores de riesgo, incluidas modificaciones en la dieta, ejercicio físico regular y técnicas de manejo del estrés. El artículo también destaca la importancia de controlar periódicamente los niveles de presión arterial como parte de un estilo de vida saludable. Además, el texto analiza los métodos modernos de diagnóstico y control de la hipertensión, incluido el uso de monitores digitales de presión arterial, la monitorización ambulatoria de la presión arterial y el papel de la telemedicina para garantizar la monitorización continua y la detección temprana de niveles anormales de presión arterial.

También se explora la eficacia de los medicamentos antihipertensivos, como los inhibidores de la ECA, los

bloqueadores de los canales de calcio y los diuréticos, para controlar la presión arterial, con recomendaciones para planes de tratamiento individualizados basados en los factores de riesgo y el historial médico específicos del paciente. Los autores enfatizan la necesidad de un enfoque integral para la prevención y el tratamiento de la hipertensión, que involucre no sólo a médicos como cardiólogos, internistas y médicos generales, sino también a dietistas, psicólogos y profesionales de la salud pública. También se discute el papel de los gobiernos en la creación de campañas de salud pública para crear conciencia sobre la hipertensión y apoyar a la población mediante la financiación de programas preventivos y terapéuticos.

Palabras clave: hipertensión arterial, manejo de la presión arterial, factores de riesgo, actividad física, dieta, enfermedad cardiovascular, diagnóstico temprano, medicamentos antihipertensivos, modificación del estilo de vida, política de salud, telemedicina, programas estatales de salud, enfoque integral.

The method of analysis used in writing this article was a detailed review of various aspects of musculoskeletal disease prevention. This included the study of scientific data, publications and current prevention programmes. The method of synthesis allowed us to create a general concept of preventive measures, combining traditional and innovative approaches. Classification and systematization involved dividing information into categories and grouping it according to common features.

An important theoretical method was the comparative analysis of different prevention approaches used in different countries, regions or health care institutions. This method will help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of different strategies and offer recommendations for improving prevention based on best practices.

Results. Diseases of the musculoskeletal system, such as osteochondrosis, arthritis, osteoporosis and others represent a serious medical and social problem, as they significantly reduce the quality of life of patients, limiting their physical activity and ability to work³.

Chronic pains, impaired mobility, deterioration of the functional state of joints and bones can also cause significant limitations in everyday life and, in extreme cases, cause disability. These diseases are often accompanied by long-term treatment, which does not always lead to full recovery, which makes the issue of their prevention extremely relevant⁴.

In this regard, the prevention of musculoskeletal disorders becomes one of the most important tasks of the modern health care system. Given the increase in life expectancy and related demographic changes, as well as the growing number of people leading sedentary lifestyles, especially in urban areas, the need to implement effective preventive measures is increasing. Prevention includes both traditional methods - physical activity, correct workplace organization and posture correction - and modern technological solutions aimed at early diagnosis and monitoring of the musculoskeletal system⁵. It is important that preventive measures are comprehensive and aimed at eliminating risk factors for disease development, maintaining physical health and raising public awareness of the importance of timely prevention.

The main risk factors contributing to the development of musculoskeletal (MSA) pathologies include both external and internal causes that can accelerate the development of diseases or worsen the musculoskeletal system^{6,7}.

The problem of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) has become increasingly important in recent decades, both at the level of individual health and in the context of public health. These diseases cover a wide range of pathologies, including osteochondrosis, osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, scoliosis and others, which negatively affect the quality of life of millions of people worldwide. Of particular concern is the fact that these diseases not only lead to a decrease in physical activity and labour capacity, but can also cause long-term disability¹⁻³.

Factors contributing to the development of MSDs include sedentary lifestyle, incorrect posture, overload caused by working conditions, genetic predisposition and unbalanced nutrition. This problem is especially acute in modern society, where a significant proportion of people spend most of their time at computers or in a sitting position, which creates additional stress on the spine and joints^{2,4}. This article aims to analyze the main approaches to the prevention of musculoskeletal disorders, taking into account modern scientific achievements and practical recommendations.

Lack of physical activity, known as hypodynamia, is one of the main reasons contributing to the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). In modern conditions, this factor is especially relevant due to the widespread sedentary lifestyle, both at work and at home. A person spends more and more time at the computer, in the car or in front of the TV, which significantly limits the natural motor activity necessary to maintain musculoskeletal health.

A sedentary lifestyle is often accompanied by excessive weight gain, which puts additional strain on joints, especially knees, hips and spine. Obesity is one of the key risk factors for the development of osteoarthritis, as excessive body weight increases the pressure on joint surfaces, causing their faster wear and destruction⁸.

Modern living conditions contribute to a decrease in physical activity. Many activities have become automated, reducing the need for movement. People spend more and more time at computers, in offices, where work is often associated with prolonged sitting. In this regard, hypodynamia affects not only the elderly, but also the younger generation.

Office workers, who spend their working day mostly sitting, are particularly affected. This puts additional strain on the spine, especially on the lumbar and cervical spine. Prolonged sitting in an uncomfortable position leads to static tension of muscles and joints, which can lead to chronic pain and the development of osteochondrosis. As a result, occupational diseases such as sedentary disease or tunnel syndrome are added to age-related changes in the musculoskeletal system.

Proper nutrition plays a critical role in maintaining musculoskeletal (MSA) health. Lack of nutrients necessary for the normal functioning of bones, joints and muscles can lead to the development of various diseases such as osteoporosis, osteoarthritis, osteochondrosis and others. Improper nutrition is not only a deficiency of certain substances, but also overeating, leading to obesity, which also has a negative impact on MSA⁹.

For the normal functioning of bone tissue and joints, the body needs a number of micronutrients such as calcium, vitamin D, magnesium, phosphorus, collagen and others. A deficiency of these substances, caused by an incomplete or unbalanced diet, can lead to weakening of bones and joints.

Calcium is the main structural component of bone tissue. Its deficiency leads to impaired bone mineralization, which causes bones to become thin and brittle. This can lead to osteoporosis, a disease in which bones become brittle and easily fractured¹⁰.

Vitamin D is essential for calcium absorption. If it is deficient, calcium cannot be efficiently absorbed from the intestines, leading to impaired bone metabolism. Vitamin D deficiency can cause rickets in children and osteomalacia (bone softening) in adults^{7,11}.

Magnesium and phosphorus are involved in bone formation and maintaining bone strength. Their deficiency also weakens bones and joints, increasing the risk of osteoporosis¹²⁻¹⁴.

Collagen is an important component of articular cartilage and connective tissue. It provides elasticity and strength to cartilage, preventing it from wearing out. A lack of protein in the diet leads to a decrease in collagen synthesis and, consequently, joint damage.

Excessive consumption of sugar and salt has a negative impact on bone and joint health. Sugar contributes to increased levels of inflammation in the body, which can worsen joint health by increasing the manifestations of arthritis. In addition, excess sugar provokes the excretion of calcium from the body, weakening bone tissue.

Excessive salt intake also adversely affects bone tissue. Salt promotes the excretion of calcium through the kidneys, which reduces its concentration in the body and can lead to weakened bones. This process increases the risk of osteoporosis and fractures¹⁵.

An unhealthy diet of overeating and excessive calorie intake leads to obesity, one of the most significant musculoskeletal risk factors. Excess weight puts extra strain on joints, especially the knees, hips and spine. This leads to premature wear and tear and increases the risk of developing diseases such as osteoarthritis.

An important aspect of nutrition for joint and bone health is consuming adequate amounts of antioxidants and omega-3 fatty acids. Antioxidants, such as vitamins C and E, protect joint tissue from free radical damage and help reduce inflammation. Antioxidant deficiencies can exacerbate inflammation and lead to the progression of degenerative joint diseases such as arthritis.

Omega-3 fatty acids have anti-inflammatory properties and support joint health. They reduce the level of inflammatory markers in the body and improve the overall health of the musculoskeletal system. Deficiency of omega-3 fatty acids can lead to increased inflammation in joints and accelerated cartilage destruction¹⁶.

Non-compliance with the rules of ergonomics is one of the most important factors contributing to the development of pathologies of the musculoskeletal apparatus (MSA), especially in modern conditions, when the majority of the population spends a significant amount of time at the computer or engages in other types of sedentary work. Ergonomics is a science that deals with the study of optimal conditions for human interaction with the environment, including workplaces, tools and equipment. Its main objective is to create conditions that help minimize stress on muscles, joints and the spine, preventing pain and the development of chronic diseases.

An improperly organized workplace is one of the most common causes of back, neck, arm and hand pain in

people working in offices. If the workplace does not comply with the principles of ergonomics, it can lead to chronic muscle strain and excessive strain on joints¹⁷.

Improper posture at the table results in an uneven distribution of the load on the spine. Prolonged sitting in a bent or twisted posture, with slouching shoulders and head tilted forward, causes excessive strain on the back and neck muscles. This can lead to chronic pain, osteochondrosis of the cervical and lumbar spine, and intervertebral hernias.

Incorrect height of the table and chair leads to uncomfortable position of the arms, which can cause shoulder, elbow and hand pain. If the chair is too low or too high, the natural curve of the spine is disturbed, increasing the load on the lumbar spine, which also contributes to the development of spinal disorders.

Working in monotonous and uncomfortable postures without the possibility to change the body position frequently can lead to a build-up of tension in certain muscles and joints. For example, sitting for long periods of time with the body tilted forward and without lumbar support can cause pain in the lumbar spine. Constant muscle strain from prolonged sitting leads to muscle fatigue and weakness, which can lead to chronic pain and the development of spinal pathology.

Another common problem is monotonous movements, especially for workers on production lines or those who constantly use a computer mouse. Constant repetitive movements of the hands and arms can lead to tendonitis and carpal tunnel syndrome (carpal tunnel syndrome), where the nerve in the wrist is compressed.

People whose work involves physical labour, such as construction workers, loaders or warehouse workers, often lift and carry heavy objects. Failure to lift heavy objects is one of the most common causes of spinal and joint injuries. For example, improper lifting of objects from the floor with straight legs and bent back creates excessive load on the lumbar spine, which can lead to the development of osteochondrosis, intervertebral hernias and pain syndrome¹⁸.

In addition, improper weight distribution when carrying objects can overload the joints of the arms, shoulders and knees, leading to their rapid wear and tear and the development of diseases such as arthritis and osteoarthritis.

Unfavorable working conditions are one of the main risk factors that contribute to the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). Depending on the occupation and the nature of the work performed, people may be exposed to various physical stresses, incorrect body positions, vibrations and other harmful factors that, over time, lead to degenerative changes in bones, joints and muscles. Let's take a closer look at how various aspects of unfavorable working conditions can contribute to the

development of OA diseases and what preventive measures can be taken.

Many occupations require employees to perform monotonous activities or to stay in the same posture for long periods of time. This could be, for example, working on a conveyor belt, assembling parts, working as a cashier, typing on a keyboard or working with hand tools. These working conditions place static stress on certain muscle groups and joints, leading to wear and tear and the premature development of degenerative diseases.

Sitting or standing for long periods of time can have a negative impact on the spine and joints. Staying in one position all the time leads to poor blood circulation in muscles and joints, which can provoke the development of diseases such as osteochondrosis, spondylosis, arthritis and myositis.

For people engaged in physical labour, it is particularly important to observe the correct technique of lifting weights and performing other work tasks involving stress on the musculoskeletal system. Failure to follow these principles leads to overstressing the spine, joints and muscles, which increases the risk of injury and chronic disease¹⁹.

In professions involving physical labour (e.g. movers, construction workers, warehouse workers), it is often necessary to lift heavy objects. Improper lifting techniques (using back strength rather than leg strength) overload the lumbar spine, which over time can lead to the development of herniated discs, protrusions and chronic pain.

Prolonged exposure to vibration leads to impaired blood circulation and innervations in the extremities, as well as degenerative changes in joints and bones. Workers, who are regularly exposed to vibration, such as from running machinery, may suffer from joint pain, muscle weakness, loss of sensation in the extremities and other symptoms of vibration sickness. Vibration can also contribute to diseases such as osteoarthritis of the joints, intervertebral herniation and other degenerative changes in the spine.

Hereditary predispositions are an important factor that can significantly influence the risk of musculoskeletal apparatus (MSA) diseases. Genetic factors determine not only predisposition to certain diseases, but also individual features of the structure and function of the musculoskeletal system, which can affect its resistance to various pathological changes. Let us consider in more detail how heredity can influence the health of the musculoskeletal system and what preventive measures can be taken to reduce the risk of disease.

Genetic factors play an important role in the formation of structural features of bones, joints and ligaments. For example, people with a family history of osteoporosis, arthritis, or other ODA diseases have a higher risk of developing them. This is because certain genetic mutations

can affect the metabolism of bone, cartilage and connective tissue.

Studies show that having close relatives with diseases such as osteoarthritis or osteoporosis increases the likelihood of their development in offspring. Hereditary factors can affect characteristics such as bone strength, ligament elasticity and joint mobility²⁰.

Genetic predisposition can also affect bone and cartilage metabolism. For example, people with a genetic predisposition to osteoporosis have reduced bone mineralization, which increases the risk of fractures and osteoporotic changes. Deficiencies of certain vitamins and micronutrients, such as vitamin D and calcium, may also be associated with hereditary factors.

People with certain genetic predispositions may have different responses to treatment for OA diseases. Genetic factors can affect the effectiveness of various drugs used to treat inflammatory joint diseases such as arthritis, making individualized treatment particularly important. Although hereditary factors cannot be changed, there are methods that can help reduce the risk of musculoskeletal diseases for people who are predisposed to them:

Psycho-emotional factors have a significant impact on the musculoskeletal system (MSA) and can contribute to the development of various diseases. Chronic stress, emotional overstrain, depression and anxiety disorders can aggravate the condition of the musculoskeletal system, cause pain syndromes and negatively affect the quality of life. Chronic stress is one of the main causes of increased muscle tension. Under conditions of stress, the body activates the sympathetic nervous system, which leads to increased levels of adrenaline and cortisol. These hormones contribute to muscle spasm, especially in the neck, shoulders and back, which can cause chronic pain.

Constant muscle tension can lead to what is known as myofascial pain syndrome, in which there is localized pain in the muscles and fascia associated with trigger points. This condition can cause secondary changes in posture and movement mechanics, which in turn leads to additional stress on the joints and spine²¹.

Environmental factors play an important role in the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). They can both contribute to the onset of pathology and worsen existing conditions. Let's consider how different environmental conditions can affect the health of the musculoskeletal system and what preventive measures can be taken to minimize the negative impact.

Air pollution caused by industrial emissions, automobiles and other sources can have harmful effects on human health. Studies show that high levels of pollution can be associated with increased inflammation in the body, which in turn can contribute to joint diseases such as osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. Inhalation of pol-

luted air can cause chronic diseases, which affects overall health, including the musculoskeletal system.

Socioeconomic factors are significant determinants of health and play an important role in the development of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). They cover a wide range of aspects such as income, access to health services, education, social support and living conditions. Let's take a closer look at how these factors affect musculoskeletal health and what measures can be taken to improve the situation.

Low-income people often have limited access to quality health care, which can lead to neglected musculoskeletal conditions. Lack of regular medical check-ups and preventive care can contribute to poor health and the development of complications. Lack of financial resources may limit the ability to purchase necessary medications, rehabilitation aids and specialized services, which in turn increases the risk of chronic diseases²².

The level of education directly affects the level of awareness of the population about risk factors of MSDs and prevention opportunities. People with a higher level of education tend to be more aware of the importance of physical activity, healthy diet and regular medical check-ups.

Discussion. The prevention of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) requires a multifaceted approach that includes not only the participation of medical specialists, but also active interaction with representatives of other spheres. This is due to the fact that the factors contributing to the development of diseases are often multifaceted and complex. Therefore, an effective solution to this problem is possible only through the joint efforts of various professionals. Let us consider the key aspects of an integrated approach.

Orthopedists and neurologists are both involved in the diagnosis and treatment of MSDs, but their efforts will be much more effective in an integrated approach. This may include joint examinations where each specialist contributes to the understanding of the patient's condition^{23,24}.

Physiotherapists help to develop individualized rehabilitation and exercise programmes, which is especially important for patients who already have problems with their musculoskeletal system. They can also educate patients on proper exercise techniques and the use of rehabilitation equipment.

Interdisciplinary consultations with doctors from different specialties discuss the patient's condition and develop joint treatment and prevention plans. This makes it possible to take into account different aspects of health and reduce the risk of recurrence.

Employers play a key role in the prevention of MSDs, especially in occupational areas where work is physically demanding or involves prolonged standing. It is impor-

tant that employers provide safe and comfortable working conditions. Regular ergonomic workplace inspections can help identify potential risks and prevent injuries and chronic diseases²⁵.

Employers can organize trainings and seminars for their employees on the prevention of MSDs. This includes training on proper work techniques, the importance of rest breaks and exercise during the working day.

Ergonomics specialists can assess the working environment and offer solutions to optimize it. This may include recommendations on furniture placement, equipment selection and workspace organization.

Designing ergonomic tools and workstations to help reduce musculoskeletal strain and minimize the risk of injury.

Ergonomic solutions should be individualized for each employee, taking into account their specific tasks, anatomical features and level of physical activity. This will help to create more comfortable working conditions that will reduce the risk of diseases. An important part of the integrated approach is informing the population about risk factors of MSDs and methods of their prevention. This can be realized through public campaigns, seminars and trainings²⁶.

Education about proper nutrition, physical activity and the importance of regular medical check-ups should also become a priority for the health care system.

It is necessary development and implementation of community-based programmes for the prevention of MSDs, targeting all segments of the population. This may include free health check-ups, group physical activity classes and community health promotion activities. Research should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of different prevention approaches. This will identify best practices and methods that can be incorporated into everyday practice.

Analyzing data on morbidity, injury and treatment outcomes will help physicians and occupational health professionals to better assess risks and develop targeted preventive measures. It is important to regularly monitor the results of prevention programmes and make necessary adjustments based on the data. This will help to maintain the relevance and effectiveness of preventive interventions²⁷.

A comprehensive approach to the prevention of musculoskeletal disorders is a prerequisite for successfully addressing this problem. It requires the involvement of a variety of professionals, including physicians, employers, ergonomists and community organizations. The joint efforts of all these actors will help to create a healthy and safe environment that will contribute to reducing morbidity and improving the quality of life of the population^{11,18}.

The state plays a key role in the organization and implementation of preventive programmes to prevent musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). Due to the growing incidence of the disease and the increasing importance of early prevention, government initiatives are necessary to ensure accessibility of preventive and rehabilitative measures for the entire population. The main functions of the government in this area include developing strategies, funding programmes, supporting research and creating conditions for intersectoral collaboration^{17,18}.

State programmes should provide free or preferential access to medical services for the prevention and treatment of MSDs. This includes physiotherapy, rehabilitation courses, consultations with specialist doctors and necessary medical equipment. The state can subsidize rehabilitation centers and programmes aimed at recovery after injuries or surgeries on the musculoskeletal system. This can be both inpatient and outpatient treatment using modern technologies (massage, kinesitherapy, therapeutic physical education).

It is necessary to build construction and modernization of sports and rehabilitation centers with modern equipment for physical exercise and rehabilitation. This will help to make physical activity accessible to all categories of citizens, which is an important factor in the prevention of MSDs. State bodies should develop and implement legislative initiatives aimed at improving working conditions, controlling employee health and introducing health protection standards. This may include establishing mandatory requirements for workplaces, compliance with ergonomics standards, and regular inspections for compliance with safety requirements.

Effective prevention of MSDs requires a multidisciplinary approach involving cooperation between different government agencies, employers and public organizations. The Ministry of Health should coordinate its efforts with other ministries, such as the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection, the Ministry of Sport, and educational authorities. This will make it possible to introduce a comprehensive approach to disease prevention at the level of the whole country.

The state can create conditions for active participation of private companies in the prevention of MSDs. For example, this can be done through tax incentives for employers introducing health protection and ergonomics programmes in the workplace.

The state plays a crucial role in creating an effective system of prevention and rehabilitation of musculoskeletal diseases. Through the development and implementation of programmes, legislative measures, funding and support for scientific research, the state can significantly reduce the incidence of musculoskeletal disorders and improve the quality of life of the population. An integrated approach, including cooperation with the private sector and scientific organizations, is a prerequisite for suc-

Prevention of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) is an urgent task for the health care system, given the growing morbidity and its impact on the quality of life of the population. Effective prevention of musculoskeletal disorders requires a comprehensive approach, including interaction between doctors of various specialties, occupational health and ergonomics specialists, as well as educational and social organizations. This approach allows taking into account all aspects of patient's health and forming a holistic prevention strategy.

ADA diseases develop under the influence of many factors, including insufficient physical activity, improper nutrition, and non-compliance with ergonomic rules, unfavorable working and socio-economic conditions. Taking this into account, prevention programmes should be multilevel and tailored to specific conditions.

The state plays a key role in creating and financing prevention programmes. Ensuring accessibility of medical services, educational initiatives and rehabilitation activities is necessary to reduce morbidity and improve the quality of life of the population. The development and implementation of legislative initiatives aimed at improving working conditions and compliance with ergonomic standards are also important steps in the prevention of musculoskeletal diseases.

Education and informing the population about risk factors of MSDs and methods of their prevention should become the main directions of state policy. This will increase health awareness and promote the formation of healthy habits among citizens.

Support of scientific research in the field of MSDs will allow improving methods of diagnostics, treatment and prevention. Introduction of new technologies and methods can significantly increase the efficiency of medical care and rehabilitation.

Prevention of musculoskeletal disorders requires a comprehensive, multifaceted approach involving all participants in the health care system and society as a whole. Government programmes aimed at educating the population, creating safe working conditions and supporting scientific research can significantly reduce the risk of diseases and improve the quality of life of citizens. Taking into account the variety of factors contributing to the development of OA diseases, it is important to continue to develop and implement effective prevention and rehabilitation measures, oriented to the current challenges and needs of the population.

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